

1 **Astrovirus infection models illustrate diarrheal disease dynamics.**

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6 Our laboratory uses next generation sequencing and advanced culture models to study and describe
7 diarrheal disease in the developed and developing world. We describe here a culture system involving in
8 vitro infection with the neurotrophic virus type Astrovirus, an agent with potential to induce diarrheal
9 disease in man.

10 Citations

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